

A comparative study on the potency of papaya (*Carica papaya*) and Tawa-Tawa (*Euphorbia hirta*) leaf extract against thrombocytopenia

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Abstract

Platelets are fragments of cells circulating in the blood stream and even though they are just cell fragments, they have many structures that stops bleeding. They stick together with each other and form a plug to seal the opening in the blood vessels. Thrombocytopenia is a condition wherein a person has a low platelet count and having a low platelet count means that the persons cut will not clot in time and have a risk of prolonged bleeding. It is caused by a lot of diseases, and the best-known cause is dengue. Thrombocytopenia is cured by intaking drugs that can improve the platelet production in the bone marrow. Alternatives such as Tawa-tawa (*Euphirbia hirta*) and papaya (*Carica papaya*) are commonly used in the Philippines to increase the production of platelets. Decoction is method to be used to extract water soluble substances that the tawa-tawa and papaya have; 2 mL, 5 mL and 10 mL solutions of the leaf extracts was being used in the rats that have thrombocytopenia induced by heparin and observed within 7-14 days. Based on the results, papaya is much more potent than tawa-tawa in increasing the platelet count of rats.

Keywords: Platelets; Thrombocytopenia; Tawa-tawa; papaya.

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Introduction

Thrombocytes are blood cells that do not have color and assist in stopping bleeding. When there is a cut or injury, these cells come together to form a plug and block the damaged area to stop the bleeding. Thrombocytopenia is a condition of abnormally low platelet count in the bone marrow to cause from mild to severe bleeding and troubles with clotting. It means there are not enough platelets in the blood. This can be passed down through families or it can be caused by certain medicines or health problems. Some diseases, like dengue, leukemia, idiopathic thrombocytopenia purpura (ITP), cancer, aplastic anemia, and drug-induced thrombocytopenic purpura (like heparin-induced thrombocytopenia) can lead to low platelet levels.

In a healthy person, the number of platelets in the blood is usually between 160 and 400 billion per liter. But in some cases, the platelet count can drop so low that it causes serious internal bleeding. In the Philippines, one of the most common causes of thrombocytopenia is dengue fever. This happens because the virus destroys platelets, traps them in the blood, and stops the bone marrow from making new ones. Dengue is a virus found mainly in tropical and subtropical areas, including the Philippines. It usually affects older children and adults. Symptoms usually appear within two to seven days after infection from *Aedes aegypti* mosquitoes, starting with fever and goes along with headache, chills, rash, and severe pain in the back, muscles, and joints. The number of platelets in the blood becomes lower, which can lead to serious problems like Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever (DHF) and Dengue Shock Syndrome (DSS), that may be deadly.

Scientists globally are trying to find better ways to treat these serious problems caused by dengue. Treatments like blood transfusions, steroid medicine, splenectomy, immunosuppressive therapy, and intravenous gamma-globulin can help with low platelet count. When platelet levels are very low, it can cause serious health issues and even death. Many treatments have harmful side effects and are expensive, so access to proper care is often limited. It is essential to discover other treatment options for low platelet count. For example, herbal treatments are often safer than traditional medicines, are easier for patients to take, are cheaper, and are widely accepted because they have been used for a long time. Recently, Tawa-tawa (*Euphorbia hirta*) and papaya (*Carica papaya*) leaves have been used in traditional medicine to treat dengue infections that cause bleeding.

Tawa-tawa is a hairy plant that grows in open grasslands, along roads, and in pathways. It is one of the most used herbs in traditional treatments in the Philippines for dengue. Even though *E. hirta* has been studied for many health benefits, not much research has been done on how well it can help with dengue (Perera et al., 2018). *Carica papaya* is a plant in the Caricaceae family, which is a flowering plant that has two seed leaves with both genders and is currently grown in many tropical countries such as the Philippines. Recent studies have shown that using this as a traditional medicine may help reduce inflammation, speed up wound healing, fight cancer, help the immune system, and act as an antioxidant (Subenthiran et al., 2013).

The study compared the effectiveness of leaf extracts from papaya (*Carica papaya*) and Tawa-Tawa (*Euphorbia hirta*) in treating thrombocytopenia. It aims to identify the blood platelet counts of the rats before the experiment and after inducing thrombocytopenia. This study can contribute to the community to enhance the awareness of the public regarding the effectiveness of natural products that can be derived from cultivated plants. The study promotes the cultivation of plants in the Philippines, which led to a greener and more balanced nature. A database was collected as baseline prevalence for the study to create a platform to new ideas and that would give guidance to others as well. This study contributed to the improvement of scientific community inside and outside the institution.

Hypothesis

Null Hypothesis

There is no significant difference in comparing the extract of papaya (*Carica papaya*) and Tawa-Tawa (*Euphorbia hirta*) leaf against thrombocytopenia.

Alternative Hypothesis

There is a significant difference in comparing the extract of papaya (*Carica papaya*) and Tawa-Tawa (*Euphorbia hirta*) leaf against thrombocytopenia.

Scope and Limitations

This study was conducted at MOTTS Animal House and Research Center at Sta. Rosa, Laguna. The study aims to know the potency of *Carica papaya* and *Euphorbia hirta* extracts to boost platelets in thrombocytopenic patients using albino rat as a subject. It is the preferred model because rats are genetically like humans. The platelet count has a resemblance to humans. The only parameter measured in the study is the blood platelet count. The researchers have used 60 male rats as subjects of the study. The chosen rat models were assigned randomly into four different groups – the papaya extract, Tawa-Tawa extract, positive control, and negative control. Data gathering procedure includes monitoring of blood platelet count of their baseline, after inducing heparin, after the treatment for seven days and observation without treatment for fourteen days. The results are determined which is more potent between papaya and Tawa-Tawa extracts.

Review of Related Literature

Tawa-tawa

Euphorbia hirta is the most used plant in traditional treatments for dengue in the Philippines. A total of 82 sources from Anda Island, Mt. Colisao, and Mt. Balungao were studied to explore the use of this plant and its effects on dengue and other diseases. High fidelity levels and corrected major use agreement of at least 35% were found for the main symptoms of dengue, especially those involving bleeding. Lower cMUAs, like 2-4%, were found to be symptoms during the recovery period. The best way of using *E. hirta* is by making decoctions from its leaves and bark, which confirmed in the treatment of dengue in the three communities (de Guzman et al., 2016). *Euphorbia hirta*, or “Tawa-tawa” in the Philippines, is a well-known folk medicine for treating dengue. Extensive research has been done on its bioactive properties, specifically its anti-dengue effects (Kumar et al., 2010; Perera et al., 2018).

The number of dengue cases increased 30 times between 1960 and 2010, which is widely believed to be due to urbanization and global warming. In a study, 125 patients with dengue fever who were treated at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital were included. The results showed that platelet count and total leukocyte count went up slightly but not enough to be significant. Hematocrit also slightly increased, but not significantly (Mir et al., 2012).

A study looked at the structure, antimicrobial, and cytotoxic properties of the extract. The tests found that the extract contained alkaloids and tannins (Enerva et al., 2015). Phytochemical tests showed that *Euphorbia hirta* contains reduced sugars, terpenoids, alkaloids, steroids, tannins, proteins, fats, oils, gums, mucilage, glycosides, saponins, coumarins, cardiac glycosides, anthraquinones, flavonoids, and phenolic compounds; while this plant also showed antioxidant, antimicrobial, sedative, anxiolytic, antiepileptic, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, antipyretic, antihistaminic, anti-asthmatic, antidiabetic, anticancer, wound healing, gastrointestinal, diuretic, antiparasitic, immunological, hepatoprotective, galactogenic, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibiting, and antidiuretic effects (Al-Snafi, 2017).

Phytochemical testing showed that the aerial parts of *E. hirta* contain alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, terpenoids, tannins, and phenols. These chemicals help the plant fight fungi, bacteria, and reduce inflammation (Arsule & Sable, 2017; Gupta et al., 2017). The study looked at how *E. hirta* affects the liver, kidney, and aorta of test animals, using electron microscopy. Using 32 male Sprague-Dawley rats, results showed that their aorta showed no changes, but the kidneys and liver had damage that got worse with higher doses. The damage started in the nuclei and spread out. This herb might act in a way like quinolone type antibiotics (Wong et al., 2013).

The study of mutagenicity of Tawa-Tawa (*Euphorbia hirta*) plant is to assess if the plant can cause a genetic material individual which can be passed on generation to another. The study utilized Ames test used for *Salmonella typhenurium* TA 98 as test strain. Acridine orange is used as the positive control, while distilled water is used as the negative control. The mutagenic activity is evaluated using “modified two-fold increase”. The observable values of visible colonies in plates treated with acridine orange were 113, 140, 161, 229, and 370 CFU/ml in 20%, 40%, 60%, 80% and 100% decoction, while the mean number is 265. On the other hand, the mean number of visible colonies in plates treated with distilled water as negative control was 79 CFU/ml. It shows that the number of visible colonies in plates treated with 60%, 80% and 100% was twice the spontaneous level (Cueme et al., 2005).

Papaya

Carica papaya is a plant in the *Caricaceae* family, which is a dicot, polygamous, and diploid plant. Its fruit is known for being rich in vitamins A and C and calcium. The main active components in the fruit are papain and chymopapain, which come from the latex in the fresh fruit, stem, and leaves. *Carica papaya* leaves have been used by people as medicine, which gives anti-inflammatory, wound healing,

antitumor, and immune-modulatory properties. Papaya fruit extract may help in treating the negative effects of dengue virus, which causes thrombocytopenia (Villanueva, 2014).

The chemical substances in papaya leaf extract were examined for the presence of several compounds like alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, reducing sugars, saponin, steroids, and tannins. When these extracts were in contact with the bacteria and fungi for as little as 1-15 minutes, their numbers also decreased. This shows that the compounds in papaya have antimicrobial properties and can be used for medicinal purposes (Shubham et al., 2019). Ethanol and n-hexane were used to extract the active chemicals from papaya. Ethanol extract had alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, and saponin, while n-hexane extract contained tannins. Using two methods such as agar well diffusion and broth dilution, this extract showed strong antibacterial potential and could be helpful in creating new antibiotics (Alorkpa et al., 2016).

Papaya leaf extracts can also stop bleeding and recent research shows that they can increase platelet count in animals affected by a drug that lowers platelets. About 21 substances were identified, including important chemicals like alkaloids, phenolics, flavonoids, and amino acids. More research is needed to find out which of these chemicals are responsible for boosting platelets, fighting cancer, treating acne, easing menstrual pain, and reducing nausea (Akhila et al., 2015).

In another study, three medicinal plants were chosen: *Carica papaya*, *Piper nigrum*, and *Agave americana*. The researchers made two types of extracts from their leaves and roots—methanolic extract and aqueous extract (water). All three plants are known for their healing qualities, and one of these is *Carica papaya*, which is used to treat malaria effectively. Results found that both extracts had a lot of alkaloids, phenols, sugars, proteins, and flavonoids. Methanolic extract showed better results than the aqueous one with saponins as the key compounds, while aqueous extract discovered some terpenoids and quinones (Singh et al., 2018).

In another study, it tries to see into how extracts from papaya leaves can help treat Dengue fever in a 45-year-old person who was bitten by a mosquito carrying the virus. Blood samples were taken to check the levels of platelets (PLT), white blood cells (WBC), and neutrophils (NEUT). These levels were 176,000 per microliter, 8,100 per microliter, and 84% respectively. After the treatment, these levels dropped to 55,000 per microliter, 3,700 per microliter, and 46%. The results showed that platelet levels increased back to 168,000 per microliter, white blood cells with 7,700 per microliter, and neutrophil levels with 78.3%. This suggests that the papaya leaf extract in water form might be helpful in treating dengue fever (Ahmad et al., 2011).

Methodology

Research Design

This research employed an experimental-comparative study to determine the potency of tawa-tawa and papaya leaves extract against thrombocytopenia. The research design is under quantitative analysis that measures the platelet count of the albino rats after inducing the papaya and tawa-tawa extracts.

Collection of Plant

Freshly collected leaves of *Euphorbia hirta* (tawa-tawa) were obtained in Las Piñas, Metro Manila and the *Carica papaya* were obtained at Dasmariñas, Cavite. Both are placed in a paper bag and brought to the University of the Philippines, Los Baños, Laguna for identification and verification.

Preparation of the Extract

Decoction is a method of boiling medicinal plants in water to get the water-soluble parts out. Fresh tawa-tawa and papaya leaves were used in the study. One thousand grams of tawa-tawa and papaya leaves were put into a pot. Then, 500 ml of water was added, and the mixture was boiled for one hour. The decoction was strained and filtered then stored in a glass container.

Preparation of Experimental Animals

The researchers selected 60 male rats which qualified to the criteria set for the study subject as follows: must be brought in one white rats' breeder only and have no physical abnormalities or deformities. The animals were observed for any signs of sickness, such as runny eyes or noses, matted fur, strange posture, swollen belly, being dehydrated, acting oddly, and staying healthy with an average weight of 120-160 grams. They were kept in a polycarbonate cage with a temperature of 20-25°C and humidity of 40-45%. The room had a dark cycle of 12 hours. During the acclimatization period, they were given normal rodent food and water and had free access to them. After they were used to the environment, thrombocytopenia was induced by giving them a subdermal injection of 0.01 mL of heparin. The rats were divided into control and experimental groups.

Toxicity Determination

The researchers determined the toxicity level of Tawa-tawa (*Euphorbia hirta*) and papaya (*Carica papaya*) leaves extracts in rats by the following concentrations: 2 mL, 5 mL and 10 mL each. The extracts were introduced to the rats by oral lavage. There were thirty rats used for the toxicity test, which were divided into two groups (tawa-tawa and papaya) with 15 rats in each group, and subdivided into three subgroups with five rats each. The first five rats of both papaya and tawa-tawa were given 2 mL of each extract, then the second batch of rats was given 5 mL of each, and the last batch of papaya and tawa-tawa rats was given 10 mL of each. The highest concentration of 10 ml of tawa-tawa and papaya extract the rats can intake was used as the concentration.

Administration of Euphorbia hirta and Carica papaya leaf extracts

There were thirty rats in the control group: for the negative control, five of which were given 10 mL distilled water, and for the positive control, five of which were given 10 mL Romiplostim by oral lavage. There were thirty rats in the experimental group which were divided into two subgroups with five rats each. Five rats were given 10 ml of papaya extract, while other five rats were given 10 mL of tawa-tawa extract by oral lavage twice a day for seven consecutive days. Before giving the animals distilled water or leaf extracts by mouth, platelet counts were determined for both the experimental and control groups to get baseline values. Platelet counts were reobserved every day for seven days after the treatments were given. Both the control and experimental group is conducted into three trials.

Collection of Blood Sample and Platelet Count Determination

To get blood samples for platelet count, 1 ml of blood was taken from the orbital plexus veins using a capillary tube, vacutainer, and EDTA tube. Platelet count determination was conducted at Motts Animal House Laboratory and Research in Sta. Rosa, Laguna, Philippines. Platelet count was determined for their baseline value, after induction of heparin, after seven days treatment of control and leaf extracts, and after seven days of observation.

Statistical Analysis

The statistical tool utilized for this study is one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to identify the significant difference between the rats administered with Tawa-tawa and papaya extracts against thrombocytopenia. The researchers compared the results of the platelet count from both the control and the experimental groups after the experimentation.

Flow Chart

Figure 1. Flow chart of the study

Results and Discussion

1. What is the platelet count of the rats before the experiment?

Table 1. Mean score for platelet count of the rats before the experiment

Rat Group	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Total Mean
Positive	365	251	292	302
Negative	234	281	331	282
Tawa-Tawa	244	268	293	268
Papaya	310	295	292	299

Table 1 shows the platelet count of the rats before the experiment. The positive group had an average platelet count of 302, while the negative group with 282. The Tawa-Tawa group had an average platelet count of 268, and the papaya group with 299. The results indicate that the platelet count of the rats

was within the average of the $160 - 460 \times 10^6/L$ normal range of blood platelets in rats. However, there are some factors that affect the low platelet count of the rats, probably the weight, food, or environment they have.

2. What are the platelet counts of the rats after inducing heparin?

Table 2. Mean score for platelet count of the rats after inducing heparin

Rat Group	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Total Mean
Positive	121	124	131	125
Negative	126	130	128	128
Tawa-Tawa	128	125	134	129
Papaya	115	126	138	126

Table 2 shows the platelet count of the rats after inducing heparin. The positive group had an average platelet count of 125, while the negative group with 128. The Tawa-Tawa group had an average platelet count of 129, while the papaya group with 126. The results indicate that the platelet count of the rats was below normal on the average of the $160 - 460 \times 10^6/L$ normal range. Therefore, heparin successfully lowered the blood platelet counts of the rats. Heparin stops blood from clotting and does not affect platelets, as it is a substance found in blood that helps form clots.

3. Is there any significant difference on the platelet counts of the rats after they intake Tawa-Tawa?

3.1 for 7 days

3.2 after 14 days

Table 3. Test for significant difference on the platelet counts of the rats after taking Tawa-Tawa for 7 days

Paired Comparison	P-values			Significance	Ho Hypothesis
	T1	T2	T3		
Tawa-Tawa vs. Positive	.829	.642	1.000	Not significant	Accept
Tawa-Tawa vs. Negative	.010	.039	.006	Significant	Reject

Table 3 shows the significant difference in the blood platelet counts of the rats after they intake Tawa-Tawa for seven days. The result of ANOVA on the significant difference from the paired comparisons, Tawa-Tawa vs. Negative revealed that the computed p-values (.010), (.039), and (.006) were below the .05 level of significance, which have a significant difference in the blood platelet count of the rats after they intake Tawa-Tawa for seven days. *Euphorbia hirta* (tawa-tawa) has effects in increasing blood platelet counts to the victim of the thrombocytopenia through the albino mice.

Table 4. Test for significant difference on the platelet counts of the rats after taking Tawa-Tawa after 14 days

Paired Comparison	P-values			Significance	Ho Hypothesis
	T1	T2	T3		
Tawa-Tawa vs. Positive	.000	1.000	1.000	T1 (significant) T2, T3 (not significant)	T1 (reject) T2, T3 (accept)
Tawa-Tawa vs. Negative	.000	.000	.000	Significant	Reject

Table 4 shows the significant difference in blood platelet counts of the rats after they intake Tawa-Tawa after 14 days. The result on the significant difference from the paired comparisons, Tawa-Tawa vs.

Positive revealed that the computed p-value (.000) was below at the .05 level of significance. Therefore, Tawa-Tawa vs. Positive of Trial 1 has a significant difference. However, Tawa-Tawa vs. Negative shows a constant computed p-value (.000) from Trials 1 to 3. To conclude, Tawa-Tawa vs. Negative showed much difference in the blood platelet count of the rats after they intake Tawa-Tawa after 14 days.

4. Is there any significant difference in the platelet counts of the rats after they intake Papaya?

4.1 for 7 days

4.2 after 14 days

Table 5. Test for significant differences on the platelet counts of the rats after taking papaya for 7 days

Paired Comparison	P-values			Significance	Ho Hypothesis
	T1	T2	T3		
Papaya vs. Positive	.996	.870	1.000	Not significant	Accept
Papaya vs. Negative	.000	.049	.008	Significant	Reject

Table 5 shows the significant difference in the blood platelet counts of the rats after they intake Papaya for seven days. The result on the significant difference from the paired comparisons, Papaya vs. Negative, revealed that the computed p-values (.000), (.049), (.008) were below at the .05 level of significance. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the blood platelet count of the rats after they intake papaya for seven days.

Table 6. Test for significant difference on the platelet counts of the rats after taking Papaya after 14 days

Paired Comparison	P-values			Significance	Ho Hypothesis
	T1	T2	T3		
Papaya vs. Positive	.253	1.000	1.000	Not significant	Accept
Papaya vs. Negative	.000	.000	.000	Significant	Reject

Table 6 shows the significant difference in the blood platelet counts of the rats after they intake papaya after 14 days. The result on the significant difference from the paired comparisons, Papaya vs. Negative, revealed that the computed p-values (.000), (.000), (.000) were below at the .05 level of significance. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the blood platelet count of the rats after they intake papaya after seven days. Fresh *Carica papaya* leaf extract has increased blood platelets and red blood cell counts in the experimental group. *Carica papaya* leaves can be used as medicine to help increase the production of platelets and red blood cells in both humans and animals with low blood cells.

5. Is there any difference in the anti-thrombocytopenic effect between Tawa-Tawa and papaya?

Figure 5 shows the comparison of anti-thrombocytopenic effects between Tawa-Tawa and papaya. Under three clinical trials with 60 rats, the graph shows that there is a close difference between the two. Platelet counts were much higher than those in the normal group after treatment. Pilot studies on dengue patients using leaf juice showed that it can increase white blood cells, platelet count, and help recovery without needing to go to the hospital (Akhila et al., 2015). Therefore, based on the figure shown above, both leaves are effective in promoting the increase of platelets, but papaya is more significant than Tawa-Tawa. Both extracts were effective, yet the figure demonstrated that Tawa-tawa is nearly equivalent to papaya (Enerva et al., 2015). Tawa-Tawa helps the body make more blood platelets and reduces the effect of viruses that attack the blood. However, papaya significantly shows a close increase level in the graph which leads the researchers to determine that papaya is more potent on treating thrombocytopenia (Ranasinghe et al., 2012). *Carica papaya* leaves have shown a positive effect on increasing platelet counts

in healthy mice. Using papaya fruit extracts may help treat the negative effects of the dengue virus, which causes low platelet counts (Villanueva, 2014).

Figure 2. Anti-Thrombocytopenic Effect Between Tawa-Tawa and Papaya

Conclusions

A study was done to know the difference in the potency of papaya (*Carica papaya*) and Tawa-tawa (*Euphorbia hirta*) leaf extract against thrombocytopenia. The study aimed at identifying the difference in the potency of papaya and tawa-tawa leaf extract against thrombocytopenia. The study showed significant difference in these two treatments, and administering tawa-tawa and papaya decoctions to animals helped increase their platelet levels. After the experiment, extracts from tawa-tawa and papaya leaves can raise platelet counts in animals with low platelets, and there were no harmful side effects. Based on the results, papaya was found to be more effective than tawa-tawa in boosting platelet levels in the rats.

Recommendations

With the results obtained from the experiment, the following recommendations are hereby made:

1. To determine the efficacy of *Euphorbia hirta* and *Carica papaya* using its minimum concentrations that will increase the platelet count of the subject specimen.
2. To assess the efficacy of the combination of both *Euphorbia hirta* and *Carica papaya* pure extracts.
3. Use other laboratory animals (e.g. rabbits, guinea pigs, hamster)
4. Use other methods in extracting *Euphorbia hirta* and *Carica papaya*.
5. To measure the bleeding and clotting time of the rats before experimentation and after experimentation.
6. Use any other educational material as a primer for community purposes.

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